

DEVELOPMENT OF COORDINATED SKILLS OF 10-11 YEARS OLD FOOTBALL PLAYERS USING SPECIAL ACROBATIC EXERCISES

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Abstract. Currently, there is a significant number of theoretical works aimed at the development of youth football and its patterns. In the theory and practice of youth football, there are not enough universal methods developed on the basis of exercises of increased coordination complexity, which helps to improve the technical skills of football players. Purpose of the study. Based on the means of increased coordination orientation, develop and experimentally substantiate the effectiveness of a methodology for improving the technical training of football players aged 10-11. Methodology and organization of the study. The studies were carried out on the basis of the Sports School for Children and Teenagers of the Tashkent region, Kibray district №16 and the football academy "Pakhtakor". The study involved 26 football players aged 10-11 years, the experimental group consisted of 12 children, the control group of 14 athletes. The distribution of physical loads was made on the basis of parametric indicators: coordination complexity, intensity, duration, number of repetitions, time of rest intervals between repetitions and series, their nature. The development of coordination complexity to improve technical skills was carried out with a variable complexity of exercises within 75–90% of the maximum level. The coordination complexity gradually increased in each microcycle; at the special preparatory and precompetitive stages, a stepwise increase was used every two weekly microcycles. Results of the study and their discussion. The results of the control of the competitive volume of the versatile ball possession technique correspond to the age-related patterns of indicators: the volume of performance data, defective%, 1×1 game, 1×1 game, the number of won and lost resistance in the support and unsupported position, the coefficient of the coordination complexity of the match. At the end of the experiment, it was revealed that the level of load indicators based on exercises of increased coordination complexity has a stable growth dynamics in the direction of the quality of actions with the ball with opposition from the opponent. Conclusions. The technique of technical training corresponds to the age characteristics of children; based on the obtained indicators, a high level of effective impact on the subjects was revealed.

Keywords: football, technical training, football players 10-11 years old, coordination of movements.

INTRODUCTION

Football, as a sport game, is a difficult sport in training young players, and the modern method of training players differs significantly from the directions of past years, when the amount of training work corresponded to the required result. Some authors [1, 3] point out in their works that further increase in the efficiency of sports reserve training should be based on the methodology of the studied sport. Training is based on modern training influences, which will allow in the further development of modern sports to increase the technical level, where it is necessary to take

into account the objective patterns of increasing technical complexity. Currently, there are a significant number of theoretical works aimed at the development of youth football and its patterns, where the main task of preparing players is rational technical training based on increased coordination complexity of exercises, this is especially necessary at the initial stage of training. In the works of the authors [2, 4, 5], the main attention is paid to a specific direction in the technical training of athletes, and there are no accents on the process that reveals the features based on special sets of exercises of complex coordination orientation. The discussion in the assessment of the old and new techniques for performing a number of football exercises continues to this day, and a qualitative breakthrough is more discussed and remains open. At the same time, until now, in the theory and practice of youth football, there is no universal methodology based on exercises of increased coordination complexity, which can contribute to the improvement of technical skills, in addition, it will allow to efficiently and rationally manage the process of technical training of football players.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The basis of the experimental methodology for the development of football players' coordination abilities is direct interaction with other motor abilities and the level of training in the direction of technique, tactics and psychology.

In the course of the study, load planning was carried out on the basis of parametric indicators: coordination complexity, intensity, duration, number of repetitions, time of rest intervals between repetitions and series, their nature. The development of types of coordination abilities was carried out with varying complexity of exercises within 75–90% of the maximum level, because exceeding the specified level, there is a distortion of the motor action. The range of coordination complexity of exercises used by us requires the inclusion of the adaptive capabilities of the body and, on the basis of this, provides an increase in the development of coordination abilities necessary for high-quality technical preparedness.

In the preparatory period, the overall level of loads of coordination complexity in the experimental training program corresponded to 45–48 hours. The level distribution of coordination complexity was chosen according to the following scheme:

- general preparatory stage (small - 30-40%; medium - 25-30%; large - 30-35%);
- special preparatory stage (small - 20-25%; medium - 32-35%; large - 40-48%);
- pre-competitive stage (small - 15–18%; medium - 30–32%; large - 50–55%).

At the general preparatory stage of the training process, the coordination the complexity of the exercises gradually increased in each microcycle, at the special preparatory and precompetitive stages, a stepwise increase was used every two weekly microcycles. At the initial stages of the preparatory period, coordination exercises were performed at low intensity, which gradually increased taking into account the increase in the level of fitness of the players.

In the process of classes, the following methodological techniques were used: non-standard starting positions; performance of tasks in a "mirror" form; changing the speed limit; changing directions when performing movements; changing the execution conditions and methods; complication of tasks based on additional movements; creation of non-standard conditions. Changes in external conditions that force football players to make variations in coordination exercises presuppose: variation in the arrangement of objects; change in the spatial boundaries in which the exercise is performed; use of additional equipment and natural environment.

Time parameters allotted for the development of types of coordination abilities: for orientation in space and time, differentiation of muscle efforts and restructuring of motor actions - 80% of the total training time, for the development of rhythmic ability, balance, response to an external stimulus

- 20%. The means of developing the abilities under consideration included acrobatic exercises:

- various somersaults and rolls; jumps with 90, 180, 270, 360° turns on the spot and in motion in different directions;
- jumping out with imitation of the game with the head in motion and from a place;
- kicks through oneself in the fall;
- tempo rolls forward with a running start, etc.

The means were used separately and in a variety of created combinations, and various game exercises were included: "tags" with a soccer ball, elements of sports games (handball, basketball), etc. On the basis of the game tools used, non-standard variants of exercises were formed to increase the level of complexity. In addition to the above, the training sessions included technical and tactical exercises with variable methods of positional activity (5×2, 7×7, 4×2, 3×2) with one and two balls of different sizes; with a limited number of touches: an educational game with several gates; educational game with taking a line or a target square; game with personal guard on a reduced area; dribbling in a confined space.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research was carried out on the basis of the Sports School for Children and Teenagers of the Tashkent region, Kibray district №16 and the Pakhtakor Academy. The pedagogical study involved 26 young football players aged 10-11 years, the experimental group consisted of 12 children, the control group of 14 athletes. The control group was engaged according to the program provided for the initial stage of sports improvement, the experimental group according to the method proposed by us, consisting of a set of special exercises aimed at increasing the level of technical preparedness based on exercises of increased coordination complexity.

The results of the control of the competitive volume of the versatile ball possession technique correspond to the age-related patterns of indicators: the volume of tactical and technical data, defective%, 1×1 game, the number of won and lost resistance in the support and unsupported position, the coefficient of coordination complexity of the match. As a result of pedagogical observations, fixing indicators with subsequent mathematical processing, it was found that at the age we are considering, football players perform an average of 439 tactical and technical actions per game (tactical and technical data) with a defect rate of 38.9%.

1x1 resistance per game (wins and losses) - 40, 1x1 resistance in support position (wins and losses) - 2.8, 1x1 resistance in unsupported position - 2.1, match coordination coefficient - 0.32.

Volume tactical and technical data: KG - 520±37.6; EG - 541±44.6. Differences were revealed in 21 tactical and technical data, this is due to an increase in the indicators of skills, knowledge and skills of a technical and tactical orientation and a qualitative selection of exercises in training sessions, in addition, the effectiveness of team actions.

Defect: CG - 37.2±2.9; EG - 34.3±2.0. In young football players from the EG, with a slight increased indicator of competitive activity, a significant increase in the quality of performing

technical actions with the ball was revealed, the indicator of defect tactical and technical data decreased by 2.0.

Game 1×1 in the support position: CG – 34±2.5; EG - 40±3.8. There is an increase in the quality of indicators in the won Resistances in the EG, this is directly related to the introduction of various exercises into the process of training sessions, characterized by coordination complexity.

defect %		resistance 1 × 1 in the supporting position, won and lost		resistance 1 × 1 in an unsupported position won and lost		KKSM	
KT	EG	KG	EG	KG	EG	KG	EG
37,2±2,9	34,3±2,0	34±2,5	40±3,8	18±2,8	20±3,2	0,33	0,43

Game 1 × 1 in an unsupported position: kg - 18 ± 2.8; EG - 20 ± 3.2. In the process of observing and mathematical processing of the obtained indicators, it was found that significant positive changes have occurred among the EG players, on the basis of this, it is necessary to condemn the qualitative selection of special exercises of increased coordination complexity included in the training process.

CONCLUSION

In the pedagogical study, experimental technologies for the technical training of young players are substantiated and developed with the use of increased coordination complexity, which ensured the formation and consolidation of motor skills at the early stage of the initial sports improvement stage. The developed technique of technical training corresponds to the preferences of children participating in the study, on the basis of the indicators obtained, a high level of effective impact on the subjects was revealed.

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